

THEORETICAL ASPECTS REGARDING THE „PERSON“ IN LAND LAW LEGAL RELATIONS

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In land law, legal norms are regulating land legal relations, which represent a complex of relations that appear between the landowners in the process of land use. Those who are under the legal norm find in its content the „model“ of behaviour they must have, whether a certain action or abstention is required from them or if they are allowed to do or not to do something.

Land legislation determines a particular notion regarding the subjects participating in land relations. Subjects of land relations are the landowners, natural persons and legal persons, public authorities in the process of land use.

Key words: person, land law, landowners, natural person, legal person.

As a system of legal norms, law is meant to regulate human's conduct in inter-individual relations and in social life, according to the general interest and generally admitted values. The mechanism of social life regulation through legal norms highlights various aspects of law's influence on society. This behaviour is reflected in the establishment and achievement of subjective rights and obligations attached to these rights, so that the relations between people take a specific form of legal relations or reports.

The norms and legal relations referred to in this case have a patrimonial character and content following the examination of the „Land Code“ project, submitted as a

legislative initiative by the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Industry of the Republic of Moldova, analysed further in the context of the present article.

Materials and methods

Elements of formal logic were frequently used during the study especially when we talk about legal norms interpretation. A particular use had the exegetical and analytic-synthetic method. The first one consists in using logic and grammatical interpretation, in order to determine the meaning of various legislative texts. The second one, starting from different legal norms analysis seeks to discover the underlying legal principles.

Results and discussions

In land law, legal norms are regulating land legal relations that represent a complex of relations, which appear between the landowners in the process of land use. Those who are under the legal norm find in its content the „model” of behaviour they must have, whether a certain action or abstention is required from them or if they are allowed to do or not to do something.

Who can be the subject of land law legal relations? Only people enjoy the valence that can bind them into legal relations and which represents legal capacity. Only they own the ability to have rights and obligations and to exercise them establishing legal relations.

Article 1 of the Land Code project submitted for endorsement, determines the regulatory object of the Code¹. The content of para. (1) establishes the land relations regulated by the normative act that appear between persons. Thus, it operates with the notion of „persons”, which, in our opinion, in the proposed variant differs from the full meaning of the term.

Etymologically, the term *person* derives from the Latin word *persona*, initially designating the mask the actor wore on stage, suggesting his role in the play. In sociology, the concept of person means the human individual socialized,

¹ <http://www.maia.gov.md/ro/proiecte-discutie/cu-privire-la-aprobarea-proiectului-codului-funciar> (accesat 26.10.2016)

characterized by a certain biological and psychological structure, integrated in a system of determined relationships over the formative process of the individual². By taking over this word in law, the purpose was to express the role of human as an actor on the legal life scene.

The *person* characterizes „the ability of a social entity, consecrated as person by the law to become legal subject, i.e. holder of rights and obligations in a determined legal relation”. Therefore, the notion of subject of law has a social and political signification at the same time.³

By limiting the discussion to civil law only, Gh. Beleiu⁴ wrote that the natural person expresses the quality of human (individual) to be a subject of civil law. Thus, the author's idea is resulting from an assertion of law theory: the *person* expresses the quality of human to be subject of law, taken either in his individuality or organizationally, but decided by the law in force and not as his natural virtue.

In addition, from the author's observation results that, this quality, decided by the law in force is depending on

² Definirea personalității, structura și dinamica ei în viața socială. Între universal și particular, interior. <http://www.naturalist.ro/societate/definirea-personalitatii-structura-si-dinamica-ei-in-viata-sociala--intre-universal-si-particular-interiorexe-1/> (accesat 30.10.2016)

³ L. Barac. Elemente de teoria dreptului. București: All Beck, 2001. p. 50

⁴ Gh. Beleiu. Drept civil. Persoane. București, 1982, p. 22.

the branch of law that defines the legal relation comprising: subject of civil law, constitutional law, criminal law, administrative law, etc.

According to the authors S. Baieș și N. Roșca⁵ the concept of *person* is a gender one and is referring to all the subjects of civil law.

These observations ensue also from the content of the Civil Code of the Republic of Moldova. The Code, in Title II from Book one, named „The persons” is referring to all the subjects of civil law⁶: „Natural person”, „Legal person” and „Participation of the Republic of Moldova and administrative – territorial units at relations/reports regulated by civil law”. Both the state and territorial administrative units participate in civil legal relations, as legal entities and therefore, the subjects of civil legal relations are the natural persons and legal persons.

We support the view that the notion of natural person belonged solely to civil law, meaning that it expressed man’s quality of being a subject of civil law. However, we must note that sometimes, especially in the specific literature, the notion of „natural person” is accompanied by the attribute „as a subject of civil law”. This happens because this concept came to be used not only in civil law, but also in

other branches of law, for expressing the quality of human of being a subject of law in one branch or another.

In para (4), article 2 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Moldova no condition is stipulated for recognizing the natural person or the legal person as subjects of civil legal relations. Therefore, subjects of civil legal relations can be all the natural persons and legal persons, even if, in the cases expressly provided by law there can be limitations referring to their participation in civil legal relations.

Land legislation defines a specific notion regarding the subjects participating in land relations. According to art.1, para (3) of the new Land Code project „land relations represent the totality of relations established between the landowners and public authorities”. Therefore, in land legislation the subjects are determined to be *landowners* or *public authorities*.

According to the land legislation in force, the *landowners*: are the „holders of the right of ownership, possession and land benefit”⁷ including landowners with title of private propriety: *citizens of the Republic of Moldova* and *foreign investors*.

From the expression, „landowners with every title are protected by the law” results that the Code recognizes the ownership of public propriety along with the private one by the landowners within

⁵ S. Baieș și N. Roșca Op. cit., p. 257.

⁶ Cod Nr. 1107 din 06.06.2002 Codul civil al R. Moldova. <http://lex.justice.md/md/325085/>

⁷ Codul funciar R. Moldova. art. 4. <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&id=313324>

the limits established by the law. Subject of land relations are the *landowners, individuals and legal entities, public authorities in the process of land use*, according to the Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court No 8 of 22 December 2014 on the practice of applying land legislation by courts⁸.

Thereby, the use of the term *natural person* in national legislation permits a more accurate delimitation of the individual subjects from legal persons.

Consequently, knowing the content (participant's subjective rights and obligations) of a legal land relation, we can determine the conduct (actions or inactions) of the participating subjects, i.e. the object of the legal relation in question. If the concrete legal relation has a land nature (or a civil one) the participating law subjects will be only holders of land rights and not civil.

To be qualified as a legal subject the person must possess, in terms of exigencies of the existing law, legal capacity, i.e. to be able to assert by its conduct the significant possession of social values accordingly to or against the acceptation given by the legislation in force.

As was said, by legal capacity we understand the general and abstract ability recognized by the law in force to a person

⁸ Plenul Curții Supreme de Justiție. Hotărîre nr. 8 din 22 decembrie 2014 cu privire la practica aplicării de către instanțele judecătorești a legislației funciare. http://jurisprudenta.csj.md/search_hot_expl.php?id=198

consecrated or recognized with the possibility of being a law subject, to enter into legal concrete relations in order to exercise certain rights and to assume certain obligations.⁹

In private law is dimensioned the legal capacity of the person having use capacity (of subjective rights and obligations) and exercise capacity (of subjective rights and obligations). The field of use capacity is not limited to private law only.

The citizens of the Republic of Moldova enjoy the rights and freedoms consecrated in the Constitution and other laws as well as the obligations provided for therein. Art. 18 para (1) of the Civil Code stipulates that „the capacity of having civil rights and obligations (capacity of use) is recognised equally to all natural persons” underlining by this the universality of the capacity of use for all individuals.

As subjects of land law the citizens have „... a permanent legal and political relationship with the Moldovan state, which generates reciprocal rights and obligations between the state and the individual”.¹⁰

The domicile and residence are attributes of personal identification and are presented as non-patrimonial rights. The legislator determines that the natural person's domicile is where he has his permanent or main residence.

⁹ Gh. Mihai. Op., cit., p.284.

¹⁰ Legea Nr. 1024 din 02.06.2000 cu privire la cetățenie. art. 3 <http://lex.justice.md/md/311522/> (accesat 30.10.2016)

Foreign citizens acting as foreign investors have the right to reside in the Republic of Moldova based on valid identity documents according to art. 6 of the Law on the legal status of foreign citizens and stateless persons in Republic of Moldova.¹¹

The concept of landowners also includes the following categories: 1) *land holders* 2) *land beneficiaries* and 3) *land possessors*.

Subject of law is considered not only the individual viewed through law prism as a natural person. Human beings can participate in the legal land circuit, (both individually, as natural persons, and collectively), when they assume the quality of collective subject of law. In law, this collective subject of law is expressed through what doctrine called as a *legal person*. The notion of *legal person* is today assimilated because the legislation also uses this terminology.

The question is whether every group of people represents a legal person or this collective must have some specific features in order to be characterized as *legal person*.

A legal person is a subject of law created by the legislator by fiction in order to allow collectives of individuals the right

to manifest themselves in legal relations similarly as a natural person.

The article 58 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Moldova regulates the following legal persons of public law: state, state bodies which by law are assigned the status of legal persons, administrative territorial units and other legal persons established according to the law, by the state, state bodies or administrative territorial units.

The *state* becomes a law subject of both internal legal relations – public or private – and is a holder of subjective public or private rights. State do not apply provisions on the establishment, reorganization, dissolution and liquidation of legal persons. The attributions of the state, as a legal person, are exercised by its bodies, within the limits of their competence.

In property relations, the state is the owner of its property. The ownership is exercised on behalf of the state by the Government¹², which "... exercises, on Parliament's assignment, the function of state property owner and creates the necessary conditions for the development of all types of property. "

The government, in his turn, may delegate this right to one or more central specialized bodies.

¹¹ Legea Nr. 275 din 10.11.1994 cu privire la statutul juridic al cetățenilor străini și al apatrizilor în Republica Moldova. art. 6. <http://lex.justice.md/md/311642/> (accesat 29.10.2016)

¹² Legea nr.64 din 1990 cu privire la Guvern, art.12. <http://lex.justice.md/md/312895/> (accesat 31.10.2016)

The Law No. 981 of 2000 on state-owned land and their delimitation¹³ provides that in the name of the Republic of Moldova, the right of possession, use and dispose of state-owned public land is attributed to the Government.

Public property belongs to the state or administrative-territorial units according to art. 127 of the Constitution (para. (3))¹⁴, where the last is organized on two levels: villages (communes), sectors and cities (municipalities) - the first level; ATU Gagauzia, the districts, Balti and Chisinau municipality - representing the second level.¹⁵

All administrative units have legal personality, patrimony and the right to regulate and administrate, within the law, in their own name and in the interests of the local population, an important part of public affairs.¹⁶

¹³ <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=310923> (accesat 31.10.2016)

¹⁴ Constituția R. Moldova din 29 iunie 1994. http://lex.justice.md/document_rom.php?id=44B9F30E:7AC17731

¹⁵ Legea Nr. 764 din 27.12.2001 privind organizarea administrativ-teritorială a Republicii Moldova. art. 4 alin. (4). <http://lex.justice.md/md/312874/>

¹⁶ Legea privind organizarea administrativ-teritorială a R. Moldova Nr. 764-XV din 27.12.2001 art. 3. <http://www.e-democracy.md/files/elections/law-atd-moldova-17-03-2011-ro.pdf>

Administrative-territorial units represent special legal persons because to them, similarly to the state, do not apply the rules governing the legal status of private legal persons.

Regardless of public or private legal status, the legal person as well as the natural person is distinguished by certain individualising elements: name, location, and nationality with no necessary connection with the name, address and citizenship of the founder - natural person or with the name, premises and nationality of the founder - legal person. In addition to the attributes mentioned above, the legal person can be identified by its logo (symbol), brand, identity number (IDNO), mail, mailbox, etc. We must also mention the fact that in land legal relations the state (its bodies, administrative - territorial units etc.) manifests itself as a legal person according to the civil doctrine.

Concluzions

In land law, the notion of *person* is referring to the subjects of law, i.e. the participants in land legal relations (landowners), which are divided in two categories: *natural* and *legal persons*.

The natural person (citizen or foreigner) is the holder of rights and obligations that form the content of land legal relations.

The legal person is a subject of law created by the legislator by fiction in order to allow collectives of individuals the right to manifest themselves in legal relations

similarly as a natural person. Legal persons of land law are created for profit. Legal persons are divided into two categories: of public and private law.

Public law legal persons are the state, state bodies, which by law are assigned the status of legal persons, administrative territorial units and other legal persons established according to the law, by the state, state bodies or administrative territorial units.

Based on the above we consider reasonable to express in a more extended content the para (1) of art. 4 „Subjects of land relations” of the Land Code project, in the following version: „Subjects of land relations are the landowners, natural and legal persons, public authorities in the process of land use.”

In paragraph d) art. 5 we propose to complete „*modifies the category of destinations of state-owned public land with the approval of first level administrative-territorial units council that own the land in question*” with the expression „*modifies the category of destinations of state-owned public land with the approval of first or second level administrative-territorial units council, or by the Decision of*

Gagauzia People’s Assembly, that own the land in question, according to the procedure stipulated in the regulation approved by the Government „.

Thus, given that, based on article 110 para (1) of the Constitution: „*The territory of the Republic of Moldova is organized administratively in administrative-territorial units: villages, cities, districts and Autonomous Territorial Unit of Gagauzia*”; article 4 para (4) „*The administrative territorial organisation of the Republic of Moldova is made on 2 levels: villages (communes), sectors and cities (municipalities) constitute the first level, districts, Chisinau municipality, Balti municipality constitute the second level*; art.1 of the Law on special legal status of Găgăuzia (Gagauz-Yeri) No 344-XIII of 23.12.94 which states that „*Găgăuzia is an autonomous territorial unit with a special status and is an integral part of the Republic of Moldova*” and finally, according to art. 1 of Law No. 24 of 04.03.2016 for amending and supplementing certain legislative acts was requested to comply with these legal provisions for art. 83 para. (3) of the Land Code in force „*Changing the destination of agricultural lands* „ in the exposed version.